

THE ETHICS OF ASSISTANCE: TEACHERS' PERCEPTION OF GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE USE AS ASSISTIVE TECHNOLOGY FOR STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES

By:

¹Dachollom Larry Habila, ²Jibo Emmanuel Mvendaga, ³Abbah O. Victor

¹Mountain Crest School, Nigeria; ²College of Education, Katsina-ala, Nigeria;

³National Open University of Nigeria;

¹larrydachollom@gmail.com ²jiboemmanuel123@gmail.com ³abbahvictor90@gmail.com

Abstract

This research was undertaken to explore teachers' perceptions of the use of generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) use as assistive technology by students with learning disabilities in Nigeria. The study adopted a qualitative and quantitative research approach using a survey design. A five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used to generate responses from 86 mainstream teachers and 32 special education teachers in primary and secondary schools. 15 teachers were interviewed. Three research questions were raised to guide the data collection: What ethical concerns do teachers identify regarding the use of generative AI by students with learning disabilities in inclusive classrooms? How do teachers perceive the potential impact of generative AI on the learning outcomes of students with learning disabilities? To what extent do ethical concerns differ among mainstream and special education teachers regarding the use of generative AI as an assistive technology by students with learning disabilities? Findings from the study reveal an existing conflict between technological developments and ethical integrity. The analysis identifies academic integrity and bias as the major ethical concerns of teachers. Again, it shows that teachers generally acknowledge that generative AI can improve the academic performance of children with learning disabilities in inclusive classrooms. However, these students are at risk of overdependence on this technology and having reduced critical thinking. Lastly, the study reveals that special education teachers are more willing to integrate this technology in inclusive classrooms, while mainstream teachers are more rigid about the idea. To facilitate the proper incorporation of generative AI in special education, this paper offers recommendations for ethical standards, professional development, and policy frameworks.

Keywords: Generative Artificial Intelligence; Chatbots; Ethical considerations; Inclusive education; Learning disabilities; Assistive technology; Teachers' perception

Introduction

Technological developments and inclusive education have opened up new learning opportunities, especially for children with learning disabilities. Over the past few decades, the field of artificial intelligence (AI) has become a major focus in research and practical applications across many different areas. AI is viewed as a system that can understand information from outside, learn from it, and use what it has learned to complete certain tasks and reach particular goals by adjusting itself as needed (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019). The beginning of using AI in teaching and learning dates back to 1924 when Sidney Pressey created a machine to help students find the right answers to multiple-choice questions (Namatherdhala et al., 2022). Since that time, AI has been used to make learning more personal for students, adjusting to their goals and preferences by looking at how they perform, their background, and how they behave (Kaplan-Rakowski et al., 2023).

The emergence of “Generative Artificial Intelligence” (GenAI) is radically transforming the educational landscape. GenAI technology has substantially changed conventional teaching patterns (Park & Kwon, 2024). Tools such as ChatGPT, Microsoft Copilot, Google Gemini, or Meta AI are being utilised by students and teachers to support their learning, complete tasks or even produce work that can be passed off as their own (DfE, 2023b). This technological shift offers exciting opportunities as well as wider ethical considerations that should be explored, especially when GenAI is utilised as assistive technology for students with learning disabilities.

Students with learning disabilities face problems with one or more basic cognitive abilities needed to understand and use a language. This may result in difficulties in reading, writing, and completing mathematical calculations (Liman, Rufus, Abubakar, & Kwalzoom, 2015). These difficulties make students with learning disabilities struggle significantly in an inclusive classroom when compared with their peers (Wood et al., 2017). Assistive technology is meant to provide support for students with learning disabilities who find school and classroom tasks significantly complex and uncomfortable regularly. With the expansion of technologies like AI leading to the emergence of new models like GenAI, opportunities abound for students with learning disabilities, making it possible for them to access previously inaccessible objectives. In addition to offering opportunities for innovation across a range of domains for students with learning disabilities, GenAI also presents barriers that must be overcome for successful implementations, including biases, misuse, and transparency (Houde et al., 2020; Schramowski et al., 2022; van Slyke et al., 2023).

There has been growing research on its adoption and how teachers perceive the integration of these technological tools in classrooms, as seen in Chan and Hu (2023). Particularly, in special education, questions on how GenAI can be implemented with principles of equity, fairness, autonomy, and informed consent are being raised (Yan et.al, 2023). However, there is a noticeable knowledge deficit in Nigeria regarding how educators view the use of GenAI. The successful deployment and use of such tools in Nigeria's educational system are severely hampered by this disparity. Exploring teachers' perception of the use of GenAI tools by students with learning disabilities offers crucial insights for developing professional development plans, curricula, and policies that promote the ethical, responsible, and successful application of AI in inclusive education.

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The aim of this study is to examine teachers' perceptions of generative artificial intelligence use as assistive technology by students with learning disabilities.

Research Questions.

1. What ethical concerns do teachers identify regarding the use of generative AI by students with learning disabilities in inclusive classrooms?
2. How do teachers perceive the potential impact of generative AI on the learning outcomes of students with learning disabilities?
3. To what extent do ethical concerns differ among mainstream and special education teachers regarding the use of generative AI as an assistive technology by students with learning disabilities?

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the mean score on ethical concerns of mainstream teachers and special education teachers.

Literature Review

Learning Disabilities and Technological Interventions

Modern education has many difficulties, especially when it comes to helping students who have specific learning disabilities. According to the World Health Organization (2015), 15% of the global population has some form of disability, and special education aims to address the needs of these individuals (Doğan & Delialioğlu, 2020). However, because learning disabilities like dyslexia, dyscalculia, and dysgraphia can be complicated and different for each person, it's important to use special methods and technology to help (American Psychiatric Association). There are many types of disabilities in special education, but learning disabilities are the most common. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD, 2006) emphasizes the right of persons with disabilities to access lifelong learning without discrimination and on an equal basis with others, and not to be excluded from mainstream education due to their disabilities. The main purpose of education for Students with disabilities is to give them the best possible support and resources in the most suitable environment, so they can get the highest level of education possible in a regular school setting (Felicia et al.FELICIA CAN'T BE A SURNAME, 2014; Hornby, 2015). However, the learning development of Students with learning disabilities in a general education classroom depends on the skilful application of teaching techniques and materials to facilitate these children's learning (Keetam & Alkahtani, 2013).

By integrating assistive technology into the school curriculum, educators can support children with special needs by offering solutions to address specific learning challenges and promote independent learning. However, choosing, getting, and using assistive technology depends on evaluating the child's needs and having professionals with the right skills to support students with learning disabilities (Campbell et al., 2006). Assistive technology helps students with disabilities access the curriculum better and improves their overall learning experience (Keetam & Alkahtani, 2013). Many assistive technology devices are available to support teachers in enhancing the

functional abilities of their students by increasing their participation in learning opportunities and involvement in activities (Starcic & Istenic, 2010). Computer-assisted instructions use different software programs that help kids improve their school performance and reach their full potential. These technologies range from simple spellcheckers to more advanced speech recognition tools and educational software. Some programs like voice recognition, word prediction, spelling checks, and math tools are helpful for students, who have certain learning difficulties (Rufus et al. 2015). When students with learning disabilities are unable to meet academic and behaviour goals, teachers need to recognize the need for appropriate technological tools and support that will help these students successfully complete required tasks.

Generative AI in Education

Artificial intelligence is a generic term used to describe diverse computer algorithms that perform tasks that would usually be carried out by human intelligence, like experiential learning, pattern recognition, decision-making, and language comprehension (Castelvecchi, 2016). Artificial intelligence has undergone significant advancement since its inception. This development can be credited to advancements in science, computer power, and emerging technologies (Kar et al. 2023). Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) is a term used to refer to a technology that has the capacity to produce seemingly original and meaningful contents in forms of text, image, or audio from training data. This technology collects and replicates structures and patterns of the training data (Cao et al., 2023). Training is the act of learning from existing materials, which create a statistical model. Generative AI then uses this statistical model to forecast what an expected response may be when presented with a prompt, which leads to the creation of new content (Brynjolfsson et al., 2023).

In education, GenAI is being used in many areas like personalized learning, creating content, and providing instant feedback. This helps teachers connect with students better and make learning more effective (Ali et al., 2021; Chiu, 2024). In the past, artificial intelligence in education has mainly focused on adaptive learning systems and learning analytics, which primarily help in monitoring student progress and performance (Ismail et al., 2023). Since the rise of GenAI, the use of these tools has grown, creating more flexible learning spaces that can adapt to each student's unique needs (Moorhouse & Kohnke, 2024).

Generative AI Ethics And Regulations

Ethical behaviour in assistive technology service delivery, counselling, psychology, and many other helping professions has been framed based on five ethical principles, “the golden five” (Kitchener, 1985), which guide professional performance and guarantee quality services. These five principles are intended to ensure client welfare, the professional’s responsibility, accountability, and professional behavior. Cottone and Tarvydas (2016) described these five principles as beneficence, nonmaleficence, Justice, Autonomy, and Fidelity.

The responsible use of generative AI in education is now very important because people believe that this technology could affect key values in science and learning, like thinking critically, being reliable, and creating new ideas (Wu, 2024). Generative AI ethics in education focuses on making

sure that its use in teaching, learning, and research follows standard practices and gives reliable outcomes. Ethics, which is a part of philosophy, sets the basis for what is right and wrong and helps decide how to judge people's actions. It gives a standard to judge whether human actions are right or wrong (Schlagwein & Willcocks, 2023). Generative AI ethics has become a central issue because these tools are now widely used, with their effects on education (Khlaif et al., 2023). Ethics offers a viable solution to shape the discussion and use of generative AI tools for teaching, research, and learning.

From a regulatory perspective, the development and application of GenAI in education poses challenges that need to be addressed through well-defined ethical frameworks. Corrigan et al. (2023) found that worries about AI in society have led to many different policies and guidelines being developed everywhere. Some of those efforts included the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in its global and more inclusive approach to AI ethics, which was adopted in November 2021 (UNESCO, 2021). In the broad view of generative AI in education, several concerns related to AI ethics highlight issues of cognitive morality (Kumar & Choudhury, 2023), accuracy (Findley, 2023), academic integrity (Rudolph et al., 2023), privacy (Mhlanga, 2023), bias (Neeley, 2023), and equitable access to technology (Whang, 2023).

The IEEE's Ethically Aligned Design, from the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers in 2020, gives important guidelines for being open, fair, and having people in charge when using autonomous systems. This helps make sure generative AI is used in a responsible way that helps society. This approach also draws on Bostrom's (2014) AI alignment theory, which emphasizes the importance of designing artificial intelligences with goals that reflect human and educational values. The effective implementation of generative AI in education also requires addressing ethical concerns related to digital equity, algorithmic bias, and student data privacy. GenAI's governance needs clear rules set by institutions that explain how, when, and why these tools can be used in schools and classrooms (Singh, 2024).

Method and Procedure

The study adopted both qualitative and quantitative research approaches using a survey research design. The survey encompassed a set of closed questions and open-ended questions, with the goal of acquiring a comprehensive viewpoint of teachers on GenAI usage by students with learning disabilities as an assistive device.

Sample: A total of 118 teachers from primary and secondary schools were sampled from the general population of teachers in Nigeria. These teachers included special education teachers (N=32) and mainstream teachers (N=86) working in inclusive schools.

Sampling technique: This study used convenience sample technique to select the participants for the study. This technique involves selecting participants who are easily accessible and readily available for the study. Specifically, the purposive sampling technique was used to sample the 118 teachers for the study.

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Data collection: The study used primary data collection instruments using a questionnaire and a semi-structured interview. A five-point Likert scale (1-Strongly Disagree; 2-Disagree; 3-Neutral; 4-Agree; 5-Strongly Agree) online questionnaire was used to generate responses from the participants. The questionnaire was divided into three sections (demography, ethical concerns regarding GenAI, and impact of GenAI). The questionnaire underwent scrutiny from experts in special education and educational technology. The questionnaire was used to generate quantitative data on teachers' perceptions of the use of ? by students with learning disabilities. The interview was conducted via phone conversation with 15 participants who had opposing responses from the questionnaire.

Data Analysis: the collected data were analysed by the descriptive statistic using SPSS package. Specifically, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the t-test of independent samples was used to answer the hypothesis. It was established that 3 would serve as the decision mean for each statement (< 3 = disagree, > 3 = agree). Thematic analysis was used to analyse responses from the semi-structured interview.

Result

Table 1: Demography of Teachers

		NUMBER	PERCENTAGE %
TEACHER ROLE	Mainstream	86	72.88%
	Special Education	32	27.12%
GRADE LEVEL	Early years/Nursery School	16	13.56%
	Elementary/Primary School	33	27.97%
	Junior Secondary School	41	34.75%
	Senior Secondary School	28	23.73%
YEARS OF EXPERIENCE	0-5 years	33	27.97%
	6-10 years	43	36.44%
	11-15 years	25	21.19%
	16+ years	17	14.41%
TRAINING ON AI	Yes	37	31.36%
	No	81	68.64%

Table 1 presents the full demographic information of the respondents. Through the survey, 72.88% of the responses came from mainstream teachers, making it the highest, while 27.12% were special education teachers. 34% of the respondents were teachers at junior secondary school making them the highest, with primary school teachers being the closest with 27.97% of the responses. Majority of the respondents have 6-10 years of teaching experience, and they form 36.44% of the respondents, while the least (14.41%) of the responses came from teachers with 16 or more years of experience. 68.64% of the teachers claimed not to have any training on AI, while 31.36% claimed to have training experience.

Research Question 1: What ethical concerns do teachers identify regarding the use of generative AI by students with learning disabilities in inclusive classrooms?

Table 2: Mean And Standard Deviation Scores on Ethical Concerns Identified by Teachers Regarding the Use of Generative AI by Students with Learning Disabilities.

NO.	STATEMENT	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	DECISION
1	I am comfortable with the use of generative AI as an assistive technology for students with learning disabilities.	3.06	1.31	Agree
2	There is a lack of clear ethical guidelines on the use of generative AI in educational settings.	3.95	0.94	Agree
3	Generative AI use by students with learning disabilities challenges existing standards for fair assessment and grading.	3.24	1.31	Agree
4	The use of generative AI raises issues of academic integrity among students with learning disabilities.	4.12	0.90	Agree
5	I am concerned that students with learning disabilities may become overly dependent on generative AI tools, reducing their personal effort in learning.	4.29	0.64	Agree
6	AI systems should have strict ethical guidelines for use with students with learning disabilities.	2.60	1.20	Disagree
7	Using generative AI could lead to unfair advantages for students with learning disabilities.	2.75	1.34	Disagree

The data present the outcome of the survey regarding ethical concerns identified by teachers. The figures indicate that the respondents agree with statements 1 through 5, with means 3.06, 3.95, 3.24, 4.12, and 4.29, respectively. However, they disagreed with statements 6 and 7, with means of 2.60 and 2.75, respectively. This shows that teachers agree that there are ethical concerns around the integration of generative AI, However, they perceive that the students with learning disabilities deserve leniency.

Research Question 2: How do teachers perceive the potential impact of generative AI on the learning outcomes of students with learning disabilities?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores on Teachers' Perception on Potential Impact of Generative AI on Learning Outcomes of Students with Learning Disabilities.

NO.	STATEMENT	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	DECISION
8	I am familiar with generative AI tools.	2.83	1.06	Disagree
9	I have observed students using generative AI tools in my classroom.	2.16	1.30	Disagree
10	Generative AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, text-to-speech, and summarizers) can help students with learning disabilities better understand content.	2.93	1.22	Disagree
11	Generative AI can support individualized learning for students with diverse learning needs.	3.36	1.12	Agree
12	Generative AI tools can help students with learning disabilities complete learning tasks more independently.	3.98	0.87	Agree
13	I believe generative AI enhances student engagement and motivation among learners with learning disabilities.	3.31	1.17	Agree
14	Generative AI helps students express their understanding better, especially those with writing difficulties.	4.04	0.85	Agree
15	The use of generative AI can improve academic performance in students with learning disabilities.	3.83	1.15	Agree
16	The use of generative AI may reduce students' ability to think critically or independently.	3.40	1.37	Agree
17	Generative AI could weaken the value of traditional learning experiences.	2.97	1.40	Disagree
18	Overreliance on generative AI may hinder skill development in students with learning disabilities.	4.19	0.86	Agree
19	I am concerned that generative AI may provide inaccurate or misleading information to students.	3.12	1.42	Agree
20	I believe that generative AI could widen the gap between students who can use it effectively and those who cannot.	4.19	0.63	Agree
21	Overall, I believe the benefits of generative AI outweigh the risks for students with learning disabilities.	2.99	1.41	Disagree
22	I would recommend the use of generative AI tools in classrooms that include students with learning disabilities.	3.07	1.27	Agree
23	I feel confident in guiding students with learning disabilities in the responsible use of generative AI.	2.25	1	Disagree
24	I believe generative AI should be formally integrated into special education support programs.	3.14	1.35	Agree

The data presented in Table 3 indicate that the respondents have a negative disposition towards statements 8 (2.83), 9 (2.16), 10 (2.93), 17 (2.97), 21 (2.99), and 23 (2.25) as indicated by the mean scores. However, the respondents maintain a positive disposition towards statements 11 (3.36), 12 (3.98), 13 (3.31), 14 (4.04), 15 (3.83), 16 (3.40), 18 (4.19), 19 (3.12), 20 (4.19), 22 (3.07), 24 (3.14) as indicated by the mean scores attached to these statements. These findings

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reveal that respondents believe there are both positive and negative impacts associated with using generative AI as assistive technology by students with learning disabilities.

Table 4: Categories of Ethical Concerns Identified by Respondents

STATEMENT	CONCERN
I AM COMFORTABLE WITH THE USE OF GENERATIVE AI AS AN ASSISTIVE TECHNOLOGY FOR STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES.	Teacher readiness
THERE IS A LACK OF CLEAR ETHICAL GUIDELINES ON THE USE OF GENERATIVE AI IN EDUCATIONAL SETTINGS.	Safety
I AM CONCERNED THAT STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES MAY BECOME OVERLY DEPENDENT ON GENERATIVE AI TOOLS, REDUCING THEIR PERSONAL EFFORT IN LEARNING.	Dependency
THE USE OF GENERATIVE AI RAISES ISSUES OF ACADEMIC INTEGRITY AMONG STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES.	Academic Integrity
USING GENERATIVE AI COULD LEAD TO UNFAIR ADVANTAGES FOR STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES.	Knowledge Bias
GENERATIVE AI USE BY STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES CHALLENGES EXISTING STANDARDS FOR FAIR ASSESSMENT AND GRADING.	Assessment Bias

Table 5: Summary of the Response Frequency and Mean Score to Ethical Concerns of Mainstream Teachers and Special Education Teachers

Concern	Number of mainstream teachers	Sum of response frequency	Mean score of mainstream teachers	Number of special ed. Teachers	Sum of response frequency	Mean of special ed. Teachers
TEACHER'S READINESS	86	249	2.90	32	112	3.5
SAFETY		340	3.95		126	3.94
DEPENDENCY		322	3.74		60	1.88
ACADEMIC INTEGRITY		386	4.49		100	3.13
KNOWLEDGE BIAS		367	4.27		139	4.34
ASSESSMENT BIAS		263	3.06		61	1.91
			$\Sigma\bar{x}= 22.41$			$\Sigma\bar{x}= 18.7$

Table 5 presents the mean scores of mainstream teachers and special education teachers on each concern. Special education teachers recorded a higher mean score (3.5) compared to mainstream teachers (2.90) on teacher readiness concern. Mainstream teachers recorded a slightly higher

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mean (3.95) on safety concerns compared to special education teachers (3,94). Similarly, they recorded a higher mean (3.74) on dependency concern compared to special education teachers (1.88). On academic integrity, mainstream teachers recorded a mean score of 4.49, which is higher than the 3.13 recorded by special education teachers. However, on knowledge bias, special education teachers scored higher with a mean of 4.34 compared to 4.27 recorded by mainstream teachers. Mainstream teachers recorded a mean score of 3.06 on assessment bias, which is higher than the 1.91 recorded by mainstream teachers.

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the mean score on ethical concerns of mainstream teachers and special education teachers.

Table 6: Summary Table of Data Computation for Research Hypothesis One

GROUPS	N	\bar{x}	s^2	DF	CALCULATED T	CRITICAL T (.05)
MAINSTREAM TEACHERS	86	22.41	3.85	116	8.34	1.980
SPECIAL ED. TEACHERS	32	18.7	6.68			

From the result presented in the table above, the t-calculated (8.34) is greater than the t-critical (1.980) for degree of freedom (df) 116 at a 0.05 level of significance. Going by the decision rule, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected, and an alternative hypothesis is stated that;

Ha1: There is a significant difference between the mean score on ethical concerns of mainstream teachers and special education teachers.

Table 7: Thematic Analysis Result

THEMES	RESPONDENTS (R)	ILLUSTRATIVE RESPONSES	CODES
ENHANCED ACCESSIBILITY	R2, R7, R12, R8	“It gives my dyslexic students instant reading support, and they feel less embarrassed asking for help.”	AI improves access to learning
ETHICAL CONCERNS	R6, R10, R14	“We don’t have a clear policy, and it’s easy for AI to be misused for cheating.”	Lack of ethical guidelines
OVERDEPENDENCE RISK	R3, R5, R9, R13	“Some students might stop trying to think for themselves if AI always gives the answer.”	Risk of dependency
EQUITY CONCERNS	R3, R6, R15	“Not all students have access to the internet or devices, so GenAI could widen gaps.”	Digital divide
SKILL ENHANCEMENT	R1, R12, R4	“GenAI helps them organize thoughts better before writing.”	Improved organization skills
NEED FOR PROFESSIONAL TRAINING	R9, R11, R14	“Teachers need training to integrate GenAI responsibly.”	Teacher capacity building

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Table 7 presents the analysis from the semi-structured interview conducted for 15 participants in the study based on their responses from the questionnaire. From the data, the following pieces of information were derived;

Enhanced Accessibility: Teachers who support generative AI highlighted its role in removing barriers to learning for students with disabilities. The technology's ability to speak text aloud, make tough parts easier to understand, and create pictures or diagrams was considered helpful and encouraging. This aligns with research that highlights the ability of assistive technologies to improve participation for learners with dyslexia and processing difficulties. However, the benefit was mostly noticed by teachers who had actually used AI in their classes, showing that being familiar with something can change how you see its value.

Ethical Concerns: Several teachers pointed out the lack of clear institutional guidelines on GenAI use, leading to uncertainty about appropriate boundaries. Without rules in place, there's a higher chance of copying work, taking easy ways to learn, and coming in contact with wrong or bad content. The ethical gap was seen as a pressing issue, especially for learners with learning disabilities who may not be well-equipped to critically evaluate GenAI outputs.

Overdependence Risk: Some Respondents said that using GenAI a lot might make students less active in thinking. They worried that students might rely on GenAI for thinking, solving problems, and being creative, which could stop them from developing their own ways of learning on their own. The concern mirrors findings from digital learning studies that note skill stagnation when assistive technologies are overused without proper scaffolding.

Equity Concerns: A common argument was that not everyone has access to GenAI. Teachers observed differences in how many students had devices, access to the internet, and their ability to use digital tools. These disparities might widen existing achievement gaps, making GenAI a privilege for some rather than an inclusive tool for all.

Skill Enhancement: Participants who support GenAI say it can help students with learning challenges improve their ability to organize thoughts and write better. They believe GenAI can offer clear examples and ready-made structures for students to follow. They said that when used on purpose, AI can act as a support system instead of something people rely on too much.

Need for Professional Training: Most Respondents, regardless of their views, agreed that the effective integration of GenAI depends on teachers' preparedness. They suggested focusing on training that covers how to use and how to guide students to use the tools ethically, choosing the right tools, and combining them effectively with teaching methods. If teachers and students aren't properly trained, they might use the technology incorrectly or miss out on its best advantages.

Discussion

The aim of the study is to find out teachers' perception on generative AI use as assistive technology by children with learning disabilities to achieve the objectives of the study, three research questions were raised: What ethical concerns do teachers identify regarding the use of generative AI by students with learning disabilities in inclusive classrooms? How do teachers

perceive the potential impact of generative AI on the learning outcomes of students with learning disabilities? To what extent do ethical concerns differ among mainstream and special education teachers regarding the use of generative AI as an assistive technology by students with learning disabilities?

The data presented in Table 2 indicate that while teachers are inclined to integrate the use of generative AI as assistive technology for students with learning disabilities, there is a persistent concern with the ethical usage of these technological tools. The major concerns identified by teachers are: lack of comprehensive ethical frameworks and guidelines for integration of these technologies in the classroom, limited knowledge and training on how to optimise these technologies, potential compromise in academic integrity, and risk related to fair assessment in inclusive classrooms. Researchers have made claims that align with the outcome of this finding. Dunn et al. (2021) claim that accountability cannot be achieved in the absence of a clear consequence for unethical actions. Without clear consequences for irresponsible actions, accountability is unattainable. This emphasises the need for guidelines and frameworks that will ensure informed, responsible, and fair usage of generative AI by students with learning disabilities. However, these ramifications should be collectively put together by every stakeholder involved, including students (Rowe et al., 2023). There is an existing gap between the existence of assistive technology and effective use by students with learning disabilities, and this gap can only be closed through coordinated efforts and strategic methods. According to Bruinsma (2011), insufficient financing, a lack of professional development or training for educators and learners, and a failure to offer assistance and direction to educators and learners may all impede the efficient use of assistive technology.

The data set presented in Table 3 reveals that teachers perceive generative AI to have both positive and negative impacts on the learning of students with learning disabilities. While they agree that generative AI generally could improve their academic performance, they hold the view that long-term learning, independence, and cognitive development are threatened by irresponsible use of these technological tools. In one of the statements, majority of the teachers acknowledge that the risk of generative AI outweighs the benefits for students with learning disabilities. The major duty of teachers is to equip students with a holistic education that would not only focus on subject knowledge but also nurtures students' overall development (Chan et al., 2017). This finding reveals the complex mixture of advantages and disadvantages of integrating generative AI in education. Similarly, studies by DfE (2023) revealed that teachers and students emphasized the advantages of enrichment in terms of expanding and broadening learning processes and offering places to start conversations, revision, and independent learning possibilities. However, concerns about the overreliance and overuse of generative AI tools and their potential to inhibit creativity and effective learning were observed.

The data presented in Tables 5 and 6 indicate that there is a significant difference between the ethical concerns of mainstream teachers and special education teachers. Mainstream teachers were concerned about teacher readiness to integrate generative AI tools in inclusive classrooms, academic integrity, and assessment fairness. Special education teachers, on the other hand, hold a more positive disposition on integrating these technological tools in an inclusive classroom with

the view that these tools present students with learning disabilities a level-playing ground with their peers. This raises a question of trust between mainstream teachers and special education teachers on the level of support students with learning disabilities deserve in an inclusive classroom. This is even more complex considering the fact that generative AI tools evolve more rapidly than the conditions for ethical usage. Another concern raised by this finding is that mainstream teachers may hold a more negative disposition towards assistive technology due to a lack of knowledge and training. Ajuwon and Chitiyo's (2015) findings discovered that lack of training is a contributing factor to why teachers do not use assistive technology in classrooms.

The data presented from the thematic analysis in Table 7 acknowledges that, with few guidelines available on how to use GenAI tools responsibly, it's hard to clearly explain what responsible use means and to properly hold students accountable. These two elements are essential for establishing accountability: without clear roles and responsibilities, students cannot be held accountable for their actions (McGrath & Whitty, 2018). Without clear consequences for poor behaviour, it's not possible to hold people accountable (Dunn et al., 2021). Thus, the creation of explicit rules and regulations that establish criteria for equity, openness, and permissible use, as well as the imposition of sanctions for careless use, are necessary for the appropriate use of GenAI tools in special education.

Conclusion

The study reveals varying perspectives on integrating generative AI as assistive technology to support the learning of children with learning disabilities in inclusive classrooms. The findings show that generative AI tools are essentially impactful on the academic performance of children with learning disabilities. However, the controversies about these tools hindering the actual essence of learning traditions, fair assessment, and long-term impact on students' critical thinking skills are still widely observed. These conflicting opinions are largely the result of the absence of a comprehensive ethical framework and guidelines for usage. While special education teachers are more flexible in terms of overlooking these concerns, mainstream teachers hold a rather strict opinion. Technology has become a part and parcel of the daily activities of individuals and societies. However, persistent uncertainty about the potential risks of using generative AI tools makes it necessary for educators and policymakers to address concerns and promote learning for students with diverse learning needs.

Recommendations

This study was embarked upon to find out the ethics of assistance: teachers' perception of generative AI use as assistive technology by students with learning disabilities. From the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made;

1. Education technology companies and learning institutions should develop targeted professional development and training for both mainstream and special education teachers to enhance their awareness, confidence, and skillfulness in implementing the use of emerging technologies such as generative AI as assistive technology for children with learning disabilities in inclusive classrooms.

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2. Comprehensive ethical frameworks and guidelines should be put together by educational policy-makers and relevant stakeholders for effective implementation of technologies like generative AI in inclusive classroom settings. This guideline should target the acceptable extent of generative AI involvement in learning tasks, students' autonomy, and strategies for fair assessment.
3. Traditional assessment models should be modified to ensure their synchronisation with the use of AI-assisted learning tools without compromising or implicating academic integrity.
4. Further studies should be carried out on the long-term impact of generative AI use by students with learning disabilities on students' independence, knowledge transfer, and lifelong learning. While teachers perceive that generative AI impacts academic performance outcomes of students with learning disabilities, there is a need to examine its impact on permanent learning.

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